

AMIP NEWSLETTER

No. 3

WGNE Atmospheric Model Intercomparison Project

October 1992

An information summary and activities description for the Atmospheric Model Intercomparison Project (AMIP) of the Working Group on Numerical Experimentation (WGNE) in support of the World Climate Research Programme. Technical and computational support for AMIP is being provided by the Environmental Sciences Division of the U. S. Department of Energy through the Program for Climate Model Diagnosis and Intercomparison (PCMDI) at the Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (LLNL) where this Newsletter is edited by Larry Gates. (Address: PCMDI, L-264, LLNL, P.O. Box 808, Livermore, CA 94550, USA)

AMIP Participation Update

The current status of the 29 atmospheric modelling groups participating in AMIP is given in the table on p.2. As may be noted, there are now 12 groups that have completed the 1979-1988 integration, while another 12 groups have the simulation "in progress". This represents considerable progress since the issuance of the previous *Newsletter* in February 1992, and it now appears that all groups will have completed the AMIP run by the autumn of 1993. In support of AMIP, the U.S. DOE has allocated computer time to the PCMDI that is sufficient for the completion of the simulations that are either in progress or yet to be started at the National Energy Research Supercomputer Center (NERSC) at Livermore.

All groups participating in AMIP are reminded of the need to prepare the AMIP standard output data and a history of state file as soon after completion of the run as possible, and to submit these data to PCMDI for archival storage, for use in the preparation of summaries for the WGNE, and for use in support of the diagnostic subprojects. The required Standard Output remains as described in the AMIP *Newsletter* No. 2 (although the contour intervals listed there are superfluous, since any required displays will be generated by PCMDI in a defined format). Those groups that have not yet started the AMIP simulation (indicated by --- in the table on p.2) should submit an estimated schedule for starting and completing the integration as soon as possible.

AMIP Diagnostic Subprojects

Ten diagnostic subprojects have so far been approved by the AMIP Panel; these are described in the table on p.3, along with their projected data requirements from the AMIP monthly-averaged Standard Output, the 6-hourly history of prognostic variables and accumulated surface fluxes, and/or other model variables. Clearly the requirements of those subprojects needing data from only the standard output or history will be the easiest to satisfy from the model results that are expected to be available at PCMDI, while other needed data will in most cases require re-entry into the model code; subprojects requiring the latter type of data (which was generally not saved during the integration) may therefore have the participation of only a subset of the AMIP modeling groups.

Several additional diagnostic subprojects are either under review or in preparation, including one on cloud radiative forcing (Jerry Potter, PCMDI), humid-

ity and soil moisture (Alan Robock, U.Md.), one on thermal forcing (Ferd Baer, U.Md.), one on stratospheric phenomena (Carlos Mechoso, UCLA), one on extreme events (drought and severe winters) (Valentin Meleshko, MGO, and Igor Trosnikov, HMC), one on North American hydrology (Pete Robertson, MSFC), and one on land surface processes (Ann Henderson-Sellers, Macquarie U.). As described in the AMIP *Newsletter* No. 2, after approval by the AMIP Panel these subproject proposals will be distributed to the AMIP modeling groups for an expression of their interest in participating and/or approval for their model's data to be used. While proposals for additional diagnostic subprojects are welcome from either the AMIP modeling participants or from the climate diagnostics community, for maximum effectiveness these should be submitted as soon as possible (and coordinated to the extent possible and appropriate with the existing subprojects).

AMIP Participation Status

Group	Contact(s)	Model	Computing @LLNL	Computing Elsewhere
BMRC	McAvaney	R31 L9		completed
CCC	Boer	T32 L10		completed
CNRM	Mahfouf/Cariolle	T42 L30		completed
COLA	Straus	R40 L18	in progress	
CSIRO	Hunt	R21 L9		completed
CSU	Randall	4°x5° L17	completed	
DNM	Galin/Dymnikov	4°x5° L7	completed	
ECMWF	Ferranti/Burridge	T42 L19	completed	
GFDL	Wetherald	R30 L9		in progress
GFDL/DERF	Miyakoda	T42 L18		completed
GISS	Lo/Del Genio	8°x10° L9		in progress
GLA	Lau/Fiorino	4°x5° L17	in progress	
HMC	Trosnikov	T21 L15	---	
IAP	Wang/Zeng	4°x5° L2	in progress	
JMA	Sato	T42 L21		---
LANL	Kao	R15 L20		in progress
LMD	Le Treut	3.6°x5.6° L11		completed
MGO	Meleshko	T30 L14	in progress	
MPI	Dümenil/Schlese	T42 L19	completed	
MRI	Kitoh/Tokioka	4°x5° L15	---	
MSFC	Fitzjarrald	T42 L12		---
NCAR	Williamson	T42 L18	completed	
NMC	van den Dool/Kalnay	T40 L18		in progress
NRL	Rosmond	T42 L18		in progress
SUNYA	Wang/Liang	R15 L12	completed	
UCLA	Mechoso	4°x5° L17	in progress	
UGAMP	Blackburn/Slingo	T42 L19	in progress	
UILL	Schlesinger	4°x5° L7	---	
UKMO	Rowell	2.5°x3.75° L20		in progress

In order to support the diagnostic sub-projects in the most effective way, the PCMDI is convening a meeting of the present and prospective subproject organizers on 16-17 November 1992 at Livermore. This meeting will review the availability of the AMIP standard output and history data at PCMDI, the consolidation of subproject requests to participating modeling groups for supplemental calculations,

possible data exchange procedures, and clarification of PCMDI's role as AMIP facilitator, data source and software provider. It is clear that successful completion of the AMIP diagnostic subprojects will require a significant commitment on the part of both the PCMDI and the participating community over the next year or two.

AMIP Diagnostic Subprojects

Number	Organizer(s)	Short Title	AMIP data requirements:		
			Standard Output	6-hr history	Other (daily)
1	J. Slingo (UGAMP) K. Sperber (PCMDI)	Synoptic to intraseasonal variability	—	u,v (200,850) P, E	OLR
2	F. Zwiers (CCC)	Interannual variability	—	ϕ (500), T(850)	—
3	S. Lambert (CCC)	Cyclone frequency	—	ϕ , u,v (300) mslp	—
4	J. Duvel (LMD) F. Cheruy (LMD)	Greenhouse sensitivity, water vapor and CRF	8	T, q profiles	LW CRF clearsky OLR cloudiness
5	D. Randall (CSU) T. Jensen (CSU) P. Gleckler (PCMDI)	Surface fluxes over ocean	7, 8, 12, 15-20	—	—
6	T. Palmer (ECMWF) M. Fennessy (COLA)	Monsoons	11, 35, 37, 39, 41, 47	u, v, χ (200) u, v (850)	—
7	W. Lau (GLA) M. Fiorino (GLA)	Hydrologic processes	—	P, E	sfc. energy fluxes precip. water runoff, soil moist.
8	J. Walsh (UILL) H. Cattle (UKMO) C. Mechoso (UCLA) D. Bromwich (Ohio St. U.)	Polar phenomena and sea ice	1, 2, 5, 7, 8, 10-17, 19	—	sfc. forcing
9	B. McAvaney (BMRC) I. Simmonds (U. Melbourne) I. James (UGAMP)	Southern Hemisphere Circulation	1-6, 7, 11-18, 21, 23, 25, 29, 35, 37	u, v, T (200, 850) u, v, T profiles	—
10	S. Tibaldi (U. Bologna)	Blocking	—	ϕ (500)	—

DRS and PCMDI Graphics Software Soft-

The DRS and PCMDI Graphics systems that are being used for storage and display of the AMIP results are available (with documentation) to all participating modeling and diagnostic groups upon request. The improved version of the PCMDI graphics software that was expected to be available in the spring of 1992 is now expected to be ready for distribution early in 1993.

The new version of PCMDI graphics (Version 2.0) will use the XView window system rather than SunView, and will provide a script language. A script may be produced during an interactive session and may be modified with a text editor. Version 2.0 will provide more user control over the format and placement of graphics and text, and will support grid transformations and computations.

Next AMIP Meeting

The next meeting of AMIP will be held in cooperation with the FANGIO project during 10-14 May 1993 in Bologna, Italy, under the sponsorship of the U.S. DOE Environmental Sciences Division/PCMDI, the University of Bologna, and the World Climate Research Programme. The AMIP portion of the joint meeting (on 10-11 May 1993) will focus on results of the AMIP simulations and on preliminary results from the AMIP diagnostic subprojects.

Invitations to this meeting have been sent to all AMIP modeling and diagnostic participants and to all participants in FANGIO, to the WGNE AMIP panel, and to representatives of the U.S. DOE and the WCRP/WGNE Secretariat. Host for the meeting will be Prof. Stefano Tibaldi of the Atmospheric Dynamics Group of Bologna University (ADGB).

AMIP Contacts

Questions, suggestions and comments on AMIP are welcome, and may be directed to the following:

DOE role	-- Mike Riches tel: (301) 903-3264 fax: (301) 903-5051	<u>PCMDI support:</u>	
WCRP role	-- Roger Newson (WCRP, Geneva)	Computer time allocation and scheduling	-- Jerry Potter tel: (510) 422-1832 fax: (510) 422-7675
PCMDI role	-- Larry Gates tel: (510) 422-7642 fax: (510) 422-7675	Programming, storage and software	-- Bob Mobley tel: (510) 422-7649 fax: (510) 422-7675
WGNE AMIP Panel	-- Larry Gates, Chairman (PCMDI, Livermore) Lennart Bengtsson (MPI, Hamburg) George Boer (CCC, Downsview) Dave Burridge (ECMWF, Reading) <i>Ex Officio</i>	Validation data	-- Stan Groch tel: (510) 423-6741 fax: (510) 422-7675
		Model documentation	-- Tom Phillips tel: (510) 422-0072 fax: (510) 422-7675
		Meeting coordination	-- Lori McDowell tel: (510) 422-7638 fax: (510) 422-7675